

Object-Oriented Representation of Electro-Mechanical Assemblies Using UML

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Abstract

The important issue of representing mechanical assemblies has been a subject of intense research over the past several years. Most electromechanical products are assemblies of several components. This paper presents an object-oriented definition of an assembly model called Open Assembly Model (OAM). The assembly model has function, form, and behavior. It defines both a system level conceptual model and the associated hierarchical relationships. The model provides a way for representing tolerance representation and propagation, kinematics representation, and engineering analysis at the system level. The assembly model is open so as to enable plug-and-play with various analysis and applications modules. A case study example is discussed to explain the Usecase analysis of the assembly model.

1 Introduction

The design of complex engineering systems is increasingly becoming a collaborative task among designers or design teams that are physically, geographically, and temporally distributed. The complexity of modern products is such that a single designer or design team can no longer manage the complete product development effort. Designers are no longer merely exchanging geometry data, but also more general knowledge about design and the product development process, including specifications, design rules, constraints, rationale, etc. Furthermore, this exchange of knowledge more and more often crosses corporate boundaries. As design become increasingly knowledge-intensive and collaborative, the need for computational frameworks to support product engineering in industry becomes more critical. Though Computer

Aided Design (CAD) vendors have developed many different ways to model parts and represent design information as constraints between parts, it is not clear that all of these representations are capturing the same level of information. The issue of exchanging parts and assembly information between modeling systems is critical for unrestricted exchange of product data. However, little has been done in terms of developing standard representations that specify assembly information and knowledge. An assembly information model contains information regarding parts and their assembly relationships. Hence, we wish to emphasize the nature and information requirements for these part features and for these assembly relationships. Further we need to address the evolution of their corresponding information models during the conceptual and detailed design stages. In this paper, we propose an integrated information model for assembly representations. This is important for the exchange of information between modeling, analysis and planning systems. The paper is organized as follows. We start with a brief review of the current work in assembly representation of products (in Section 1.1). We present the object-oriented representation of electro-mechanical assemblies using Unified Modeling Language (UML) [1] in Section 2. In Section 3, we discuss a Usecase analysis of the Assembly model. Finally, the conclusions and further research work are presented in Section 4.

1.1 Previous Work and Current Status

ISO 10303-Part 44 [2] provides for some limited assembly design representations that capture the assembly structure and the kinematic joint information. The assembly model reported here establishes a neutral representation of assemblies of products, which are composed of sets of components. In this model, the complete products are called assemblies, and the components at the lowest levels in the assemblies are called parts. The model focuses on the hierarchy of the product, and on the position and orientation between parts. One of the primary features de-

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defined in ISO 10303 is that it provides a data modeler to generate various types of product data structures (e.g., Bill-Of-Materials (BOM), parts list, etc.) using the same primitive entities. However, it should be noted that ISO 10303 does not adequately address the following: (1) The relationship among different product definitions for the same product (e.g., the relationship of a product definition for a component in a preliminary design to a corresponding product definition for the same component in a detailed design is not captured), (2) The change process for a product including the reasons for the change, and (3) The decisions made and their rationale, for the entire product life cycle. ISO working group (TC 184/SC4/WG12) [3] has proposed to enhance the STEP's assembly representation. In their proposal, they have defined detailed geometric information not only for hierarchical relationship but for peer to peer relationships among component parts via assembly features. Geometric constraints among component parts at the detailed geometric element level are also enabled. They have included more information on component association and included detailed information about appropriate assembly features involved in component associations. It should be noted that the ISO proposal does not cover configuration management of assemblies and components. Although the proposal outlined the possible applications of the proposed assembly representation in four areas: kinematic analysis of assemblies; animation of assemblies; assembly/disassembly process planning; and tolerance analysis and synthesis, the actual application methodologies were not identified or reported.

NIST has been actively involved in identifying and developing representational methodologies for the next generation of assembly-related standards. Our research seeks ways to assist designers with assembly considerations throughout the different phases of the complete product realization process, from conception to assembly analysis and final process plan development. Readers are encouraged to refer to [4, 5] for a brief summary of several ongoing research activities at NIST regarding assembly related activities. The design for tolerance of electro-mechanical assemblies project [4, 6] advocates a more general and unified assembly representation scheme for proactive uses in the conceptual and detailed design phases. This scheme includes function, behavior and tolerance information models, along with other assembly information i.e., the geometric, topological and mating constraints, in the assembly data model. The primary goal of this project was to integrate comprehensive function, assembly (artifact) and behavior models. The FAB (**F**unction-**A**ssembly-**B**ehavior) data model was developed to capture product development-related issues from the conceptual design stage to the detailed assembly building process. The proposed aggregate

structure of function, behavior and assembly in this data model can support conceptual design as well as design for manufacturing and assembly, starting from an early design stage.

The primary objective of the integrated NIST Core Product Model (CPM) [7] is to provide a base-level product model that is: not tied to any vendor software; open; non-proprietary; simple; generic; expandable; independent of any one product development process; and capable of capturing the engineering context that is most commonly shared in product development activities. The core model focuses on artifact representation including function, form, behavior and material, physical and functional decompositions, and relationships among these concepts. The model is heavily influenced by the Entity-Relationship data model; accordingly, it consists of two sets of classes, called object and relationship, equivalent to the UML class and association class, respectively. It is expected that the core model may eventually serve as a precursor for STEP in the lifecycle of a product, capturing all information relevant to the ongoing design process until the product design is firmed up, approved and committed to purchasing or manufacturing.

The CPM provides several primitives, which we discuss next. The CPM focuses on artifact representation including function, form, behavior, and material, physical, and functional decompositions, and relationships among these concepts. An **Artifact** refers to a product or one of its components. (We use bold face notation for classes and packages). It is the aggregation of **Function**, **Form**, and **Behavior**. **Form** is the aggregation of **Geometry** and **Material**. In addition, an **Artifact** has **Specification** and **Feature**. The **Specification** refers to the general information that contains all the design requirements pertaining to the artifacts function or form. **Feature** represents any information in the **Artifact** that is an aggregation of **Function** and **Form**; purely geometric constructs are not treated as features in the CPM. For more information on the CPM, including the relationships (associations) defined between the classes shown, please refer to [7].

In the ESPRIT funded project, known as MOKA [8], the product model supports five distinct views of the product: structure, function, behavior, technology, and representation. These views represent different perspectives of the underlying product model. The MOKA product representation model is similar to the FAB and CPM models and it includes a considerable amount of assembly information. However, the MOKA system does not represent kinematics, tolerance, and assembly and parametric constraints. However the constraints defined in MOKA cannot handle mating, assembly, and parametric constraints. The proposed model OAM can handle these types of constraints

in addition to the constraints described in MOKA. These are essential for assembly, kinematics, and tolerance representations. The representations of the physical structure are supported within MOKA by the representation View, which includes geometry, and the finite element method (FEM). A separate Class structure for FEM may be useful in design and analysis integration. However, it is included more as a place holder.

There are some academic systems that offer some facilities to represent assembly information. One such system developed by Whitney and Mantripragada [9] represents the high-level assembly information as the key characteristics. The chains of dimensional relationships and constraints in the product are handled by the so-called Datum Flow Chain concept. One of the earlier work on assembly modeling was reported in [10]. The system of van der Net [11] focuses on designing assemblies taking into account requirements from the assembly process planning phase, in order to prevent design errors, reduce lead times, and be able to automate process planning. These requirements are captured in the assembly by specifying geometric, assembly and tolerance specific relations on and between the assembled parts.

2 UML Representation of Assembly Model

We now discuss the class definitions and structure of the assembly model. We use UML notation and diagrams to explain the assembly model. We also use a bold face convention to denote classes. The assembly model's class diagram is made up of multiple sub-diagrams, each of which is represented by a Package. The concept of a Package is that of a collection of multiple classes [1] that can be used as a namespace.

2.1 Main Schema of the Assembly model

The main assembly model schema is depicted in Figure 1. The model incorporates information about assembly relationship and component composition (part-of). The assembly relationship is represented by a class named **AssemblyAssociation**. The component composition of the assembly is modeled using the part-of relationship. An **Assembly** is decomposed into subassemblies and parts. A **Part** is the lowest level component. The information for the **Artifact** class is inherited by the **Assembly**, and **Part** classes. The information for the **Feature** class is inherited by the **OAMFeature** class. The diagram shows that an assembly or a sub-assembly is made up of at least two parts.

Each assembly component, whether a sub-assembly or part, is made up of one or more features, represented in the model by the **OAMFeature** class, where OAM refers

Figure 1: Main Schema of Assembly

to Open Assembly Model. The **Assembly** and **Part** classes are subclasses of the CPM **Artifact** class, inheriting its definition, and **OAMFeature** is a subclass of the CPM **Feature** class.

The package **AssemblyAssociation** represents the component assembly relationship of the assembly. It is the aggregation of one or more **ArtifactAssociations**. Figure 2 shows the package **ArtifactAssociation** which describes the assembly relationship between artifacts. The **ArtifactAssociation** class represents the assembly relationship between two or more artifacts. For most cases, the relationship involves two or more artifacts. In some cases, however, it may involve only one artifact to represent a special situation. Such a case may occur when an artifact should be indicated to be fixed in space to anchor the entire assembly with respect to the ground. It can also occur when a kinematic information between an artifact at input point and the ground should be captured. Such cases can be regarded as the relationship between the ground and an artifact. Hence, we allow the artifact association with one artifact associated in these special cases. The **ArtifactAssociation** is further specialized into the following classes **PositionOrientation**, **RelativeMotion** and **Connection**. **PositionOrientation** represents the relative position and orientation between two or more artifacts which are not physically connected with one another. This entity is used to describe the constraints on the relative position and orientation between two or more artifacts. **RelativeMotion** represents the relative motions between two or more artifacts which are not physically connected with one another. This entity is used to describe the constraints on the relative motions between two or more artifacts. For instance, the relative motion of a robot hand against the base of a robot can be represented

Figure 2: Artifact Association

by this class. In this case, the robot hand is not connected directly to the base.

Connection represents the connection between artifacts which are physically connected to one another. As Figure 2 shows, **Connection** is further specialized as **FixedConnection**, **MovableConnection** or **IntermittentConnection**. **FixedConnection** represents a connection in which the participating artifacts are physically connected and fixed. It is used to describe the type and/or properties of fixed joints. For example, attachment (fastening) with screw, pin, or rivet; bonding such as welding, adhering, brazing, or soldering, and fitting (clearance fit, tight or interference fit) are fixed connections. **MovableConnection** represents the connection in which the participating artifacts are physically connected and movable with respect to one another. It is used to describe the type and/or properties of kinematic joints. Typical examples of movable connections are kinematic pairs such as shaft-bearing joints or gear joints. **IntermittentConnection** represents the connection in which the participating artifacts are physically connected only intermittently. It is used to describe the type and/or properties of intermittently-connected components. For example, limit switches, contacts using bimetal, or pressure valves with springs are intermittent connections.

2.2 OAMFeature

OAMFeature (see Figure 3) is a subclass of **Feature** defined in CPM. It inherits the function and behavior information from **Feature**. **OAMFeature** has tolerance information which is represented by the class **Tolerance**. **OAMFeature** has subclasses **AssemblyFeature** and **CompositeFeature**. **CompositeFeature** represents a composite feature that can be decomposed into multiple simple features. The Figure 3 also shows the package

AssemblyFeature. **AssemblyFeature** (defined in package **AssemblyFeature**) specifies the relationships between assembled components.

Figure 3 shows the relationship between classes that are related to assembly features. **AssemblyFeature**, a subclass of **OAMFeature**, represents assembly features (e.g., geometrical entities such as faces, edges or vertices of any parts of entities). Assembly features are a collection of geometric entities of artifacts. They may be partial shape elements of any artifact. For example, consider a shaft-bearing connection. The bearing's hole and the shaft's cylinder can be viewed as the assembly features that describe the physical connection between the bearing and the shaft. We can also think of geometric elements such as planes, screws and nuts, spheres, cones, and tori as assembly features. **AssemblyFeatureAssociation** represents the association between mating assembly features through which relevant artifacts are associated. Since associated artifacts can have multiple feature-level associations when assembled, one artifact association may have two assembly features associations at the same time. That is, an artifact association is the aggregation of assembly feature associations as shown in Figure 3. This relationship is also identified by the multiplicity symbol 1..* (see Figure 3). Any assembly feature association relates in general to two or more assembly features. However, as in the special case mentioned earlier where an artifact association involves only one artifact, it may involve only one assembly feature. Hence, the **AssemblyFeature** end of the association with **AssemblyFeatureAssociation** in Figure 3 is denoted by the multiplicity symbol 1..*, not by the multiplicity symbol 2..*. The assembly relationship between two or more assembly features is represented by the class **AssemblyFeatureAssociationRepresentation**. This diagram also shows that the **ArtifactAssociation** is the aggregation of **AssemblyFeatureAssociation** and has tolerance information represented by the **Tolerance** class.

The specific contents of any assembly feature association are described by the **AssemblyFeatureAssociationRepresentation**. This class is an aggregation of parametric assembly constraints, a kinematic pair, and/or a relative motion between assembly features as shown in Figure 4.

ParametricAssemblyConstraint represents the parametric assembly constraints of assembly feature associations. It is used to specify explicit geometric constraints between artifacts of an assembled product. The parametric assembly constraints are intended to control the position and orientation of artifacts in an assembly. Parametric assembly constraints are defined in ISO 10303 Part 108 [12] (under ballot). The class **ParametricAssemblyConstraint** defines the assembly constraints (position and orientation) between two parts in an assembly. This

Figure 3: OAMFeature

Figure 4: Assembly Feature Association Representation

class is further specialized into specific types of assembly constraints. The following classes are defined: **Parallel**, **ParallelWithDimension**, **SurfaceDistanceWithDimension**, **AngleWithDimension**, **Perpendicular**, **Incidence**, **Coaxial**, **Tangent**, and **FixedComponent**.

KinematicPair defines the kinematic constraints between two adjacent artifacts (links) at a joint. The kinematic structure schema in ISO 10303 Part 105 defines the kinematic structure of a mechanical product in terms of links, pairs, and joints. The kinematic pair represents the geometric aspects of the kinematic constraints of motion between two assembled components. **KinematicPath** represents the relative motion between artifacts. The kinematic motion schema in ISO 10303 Part 105 defines kinematic motion. It is also used to represent the relative motion between artifacts.

Tolerance

Tolerancing is a critical issue in the design of electro-mechanical assemblies. Tolerancing includes both tolerance analysis and tolerance synthesis. Any proactive approach to assembly or tolerance analysis in the early design stages will involve making decisions with incomplete information models. In order to carry out early tolerance synthesis and analysis in the conceptual product design stage, we include function, tolerance, and behavior information into the assembly model that will allow analysis and synthesis of tolerances, even with incomplete data sets. To do this we define a class structure for tolerance specification. We describe this in **Tolerance** package (see Figure 5).

DimensionalTolerance typically controls the variability of linear dimensions that describe location, size and angle; this is also known as tolerancing of perfect form. **GeometricTolerance** is the general term applied to the category of tolerances used to control shape, position, and runout. It enables tolerances to be placed on attributes of features, where a feature is one or more pieces of part surface; feature attributes include size (for certain features), position (certain features), form (flatness, cylindricity, etc.), and relation (e.g. perpendicular-to).

The class **GeometricTolerance** is further specialized into the following: (1) **FormTolerance** (**StraightnessTolerance**, **FlatnessTolerance**, **CircularityTolerance**, and **CylindricityTolerance**); (2) **ProfileTolerance** (which is further specialized into **ProfileSurfaceTolerance**, and **ProfileofaLine**); (3) **RunoutTolerance** (which is further specialized into **Circularrunout**, and **Totalrunout**); (4) **OrientationTolerance** (which is further specialized into **AngularityTolerance**, **ParallelismTolerance**, and **PerpendicularityTolerance**); and (4) **LocationTolerance** (which is further specialized into **PositionTolerance**, **ConcentricityTolerance**, and **SymmetryTolerance**);

Datum is a theoretically exact or a simulated piece of geometry, such as a point, a line, or a plane, from which a tolerance is referenced. **DatumFeature** is a physical feature that is applied to establish a datum. **FeatureOfSize** is a feature that is associated with a size dimension, such as the diameter of a spherical or cylindrical surface and the distance between two parallel planes. **StatisticalControl** is a specification that incorporates statistical process controls on the toleranced feature in manufacturing.

3 Usecase Study

This section describes the assembly model of an industrial device, a planetary gear system. The planetary gear system is used to demonstrate the assembly and tolerance model. Figure 6 shows a solid model of the gear system,

Figure 5: Tolerance Package

Figure 6: Planetary Gear System

generated using a CAD system. The assembly hierarchy for the planetary gear system is assumed to be composed of two parts, namely, the input-housing and sun gear, and three subassemblies, as shown in Figure 7. The three subassemblies are: (1) the output end assembly that contains the two bearings, the washer, and the output housing; (2) the ring gear assembly that consists of the ring gear and two ring-gear pins; and (3) the planet gear carrier assembly that consists of three planet gears and the planet carrier assembly, which further decomposes into an output shaft and three planet-gear pins. The sequence of part assembly descriptions does not imply an assembly sequence. The assembly sequencing task is outside the scope of this paper.

The hierarchical relationships between the artifacts of the planetary gear system can be represented as an instance diagram as shown in Figure 8. The elements are underlined to show that they are instances. The names take the following form *instance name: class name*. The instances rep-

Figure 7: Assembly Hierarchy and Associations

resent the hierarchical relations between artifacts (assembly, subassembly, and part). The root node is the entire assembly, the interior nodes are sub-assemblies, and the leaf nodes are component parts. The **AssemblyAssociation** instance contains other types of information such as mating conditions, kinematic relations, assembly features, details of which are not included here. **AssemblyAssociation** is an aggregation of **ArtifactAssociation** instances. The artifact associations hold relational information such as mating conditions, kinematic pairs, and assemblies between assembly features. For the gear head assembly shown in Figure 6, a graph of artifact associations is shown in Figure 7. The solid lines indicate the artifact associations and the dotted lines portray the hierarchical assembly relations.

Artifacts	Assembly Features	Assembly Constraints	Kinematic Relations
Output shaft @Planet carrier assembly @Planet gear-carrier	Bearing seat of output shaft surface (bearingSeat3:AF)	Coaxial Parallel Angle with dimension	Relative rotation (rp5:RevolutePair)
Bearing 1 @Output housing	Inner race surface of bearing (innerRace1:AF)		
Bearing 2 @Output housing	Inner race surface of bearing (innerRace2:AF)		

Table 1: Assembly Relations Between Output Housing Assembly and Planet Gear-Carrier Assembly

Let us consider the assembly relation *mc4* between the output housing assembly and planet gear-carrier assembly.

